

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AT SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Abstract:

This article discussed modern methods of teaching English at secondary school. Currently, teaching of foreign languages is one of the most relevant process all over the world. Therefore, the use of modern media in the educational system is in full swing. It provides many facilities to teachers in the learning process not only for teachers but also it helps to school children. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is the formation and development of a communicative culture of schoolers teaching practical msytery of the English language.

Key words: schoolers, teaching practical mystery, modernization, education system, learning process, foreign language.

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Foreign languages are becoming more and more popular and preferred everyday life. It is useful to know many languages, and this article also mention that one of the common languages international communications is English. Learning English has becoming popular among the modern society. A foreign language has been a compulsory subject of instructions at secondary school. School age from the point of view of psychology and pedagogy, is the best time to start learning foreign language. Based on this we can conclude the sooner you start learning foreign languages the more effectively, faster and easier it will be give given to him or her, and the more languages, he or she calmly in the future [1].

English is often considered one of the most difficult languages to learn fluently, if you haven't grown up speaking it. As a second language at secondary school mastering secondary level English can be a challenge, but helping your student gain a strong command of the language is far from possible. One more important thing if teacher use modern methods of teaching, learning process will be not challengeable. Here are some modern methods of teaching English at school [4;94].

1. Stimulate debate and discussion

Encourage your students to debate on a variety of subjects; fictional characters from a popular television show "What if..." future scenarios, improvements they would to see in their community or environment, and whatever else gets them talking. Bring up some sensational celebrity gossip every now and then, or taboo ideas that other teachers won't touch. Staying outside the established syllabus gives students

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more freedom to express themselves' debating brings an element of competition that is entirely language- based.

1. Try Immersive Reading Activities

Studying English literature is one of the most effective ways to develop fluency in reading, writing and to some extent, speaking the language. Instead of focusing on formal acquisition of literary concepts alone, though, engage your student with creative immersion activities.

Get them compose music, re- enact or paint something about which they are currently reading. Let them work in groups and share ideas on certain projects, but include solo activities that encourage them to find their own unique meanings in poems, stories, and other literature as well [5].

2. Boost Writing Skills in Fun Ways

There is only way to really gain written fluency in any language- practice, Practice, practice. Unfortunately, most students today rely on smartphones or computers to correct anything they write, whether it's an instant message or a homework paper.

You need to make writing seem more interesting, especially when you are competing against popular slang and "SMS language" that seem to be killing the written word. Try collaborative projects with a modern twist. Set up a blog where students can regularly publish poetry, translations, short stories or even memes as a group.

3. Create a List of Grammar- Based App

Teaching students the concepts of grammar and composition is less about theory and more about practice. The number of hours they spend in your class is limited, but they're likely to have 24\7 access to a smartphone, tablet or laptop- use this to your advantage.

Leverage the power of web- based tools, by creating a list of the best apps and games that can be used for teaching English. Share those with your students to help them build their vocabulary, explore interactive platforms for learning, and improve their grammar through constant practice and exposure.

4. Maximize the Potential of Online Tools

Use smart classroom technology to monitor students' progress, encourage them to try out online learning tools and interact with English speakers on social media platforms and etc. These unconventional methods of teaching resonate with young students who are completely at home on the web.

The internet offers a practically endless array of reading material for students learning English, right from e- books and stories to social media content, translation tools and blog posts. While speaking a language is important, reading allows students to grasp concepts autonomously and build their vocabulary faster [3;335-336].

5. Build an Inspirational Study Environment

Do not expect your students to get excited about learning if the classroom. Environment isn't designed to inspire them. There are number of ways to boost the learning appeal of a certain space, so get creative and set up a zone that encourages and motivates students.

If you are online English tutor, put in the time and effort to create a great website with well- written content and audio-visual aids. If you are teaching English in a

physical space, include resources that will prompts students to learn. For instance, create reading areas with a variety of material from different authors and genres.

6. Use Self- and Peer- Assessment for Motivation

Everyone learners at their own pace, but no one can resist the chance to mark someone else's work or their own. This form of assessment allows students to grasp the values behind a certain concept, as well as understanding where they could improve [2;123].

Reviewing each other's work and their own helps boost confidence in their abilities as well as motivate them through healthy competition. Guide them through the process with a marking model, and encourage them to look for examples of grammatical concepts that they may need to practice more [4;93].

In conclusion

Nowadays, English is thought at school, and there several methods of teaching English. Teaching with the help of modern methods is becoming more and more effective. Teaching with the help of modern technologies for example, the presence of various blogs based on language teaching on platforms, Telegram or Instagram. Because nowadays young people are spending most of their time on different platforms like above.

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